

Variability of pigment in Indian upland rices

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Pigment traits in 6 plant parts were identified in 98 upland rices using the I.S.I. India color chart.

Of 58 pigments found, seedling (S) showed 3, leaf (L) 12, node (N) 15, internode (I) 15, grain (G) 20, and kernel (K) 25 (see table).

Serial numbers assigned each pigment:

1 = dark green	30 = light buff
2 = pale green	31 = deep buff
3 = green	32 = ivory
4 = cypress green	33 = orange
5 = sage green	34 = brown
6 = beech brown	35 = middle buff
7 = grass green	36 = pale cream
8 = light bronze green	37 = golden brown
9 = sea green	38 = sight buff
10 = scamic	39 = adm gray
11 = scamic green	40 = middle brown
12 = middle bronze green	41 = new ivory
13 = light olive green	42 = salmon pink
14 = eau-de-nil	43 = light salmon pink
15 = leaf brown	44 = broke white
16 = lincoln green	45 = orange brown
17 = chocolate	46 = deep rose
18 = olive green	47 = pale rose
19 = light purple brown	48 = beige
20 = light brunswick green	49 = terracota
21 = red oxide	50 = kenetian
22 = service brown	51 = new mushroom
23 = deep indian green	52 = broken brown
24 = brilliant green	53 = primrose
25 = deep brunswick	54 = rose pink
26 = light cream	55 = mimosa
27 = pale huff	56 = traffic red
28 = light brown	57 = crimson
29 = nut brown	58 = special gray

Distribution of pigments in 98 upland rice cultivars in 11 states, India, 1986

Cultivar	Pigments					
	S	L	N	I	G	K
<i>Andhra Pradesh</i>						
Caveri	3	5	7	5	27	44
Rasi	1	8	7	7	27	36
<i>Assam</i>						
ARC11775	3	18	5	8	27	41
<i>Bihar</i>						
Browngora	2	18	7	9	27	37

Table continued.

Cultivar	Pigments					
	S	L	N	I	G	K
Karangagora	2	4	16	8	28	50
Nonhigora	1	24	7	9	28	45
<i>Gujarat</i>						
Deharadun-2-13-18-12	1	5	7	8	27	44
Junagarh 68	3	7	9	14	27	44
Kolhapur scented	3	18	4	8	37	51
<i>Maharashtra</i>						
Ambemohar	2	4	5	8	27	41
Improved Raskadam	1	5	13	8	30	47
Nagpur 14	1	24	7	9	27	21
Nagpur 22	3	18	4	8	27	36
Nagpur 27	3	5	8	8	27	41
Raskadam	3	9	9	14	37	55
Tetco	3	7	9	14	28	50
<i>Meghalaya</i>						
Mirkirak	2	4	5	13	27	47
<i>Orissa</i>						
Kalkeri	3	4	7	9	29	37
<i>Punjab</i>						
Jhona 349	2	18	7	9	27	43
Lalnakanda	3	4	7	9	28	50
<i>Tamil Nadu</i>						
Poongar	1	4	13	22	6	28
Chitrikar	1	20	7	9	28	37
Panke	2	4	7	8	32	37
Chali	1	18	7	9	32	45
Chipti	1	4	4	21	17	35
Viagai	1	18	7	14	36	41
Bhattadhan	2	5	4	18	31	46
Surajmukhi	1	12	5	22	35	43
<i>Uttar Pradesh</i>						
Anjani	1	18	4	19	26	28
Bagri	3	4	6	20	27	42
Bagri white	2	4	7	5	27	37
Bagri red	2	5	8	8	28	15
Beni	1	4	9	14	22	42
Bakki	3	20	7	9	29	43
Badamfarm	3	18	7	13	30	44
Bendi	1	18	7	8	30	44
Bhadailakala	2	8	7	5	17	45
Champa	3	9	7	9	28	37
Chingurdi	3	18	7	1	6	42
Dehula A	2	4	8	8	27	37
Dehula B	1	5	9	14	31	47
Dudhi	1	5	10	17	34	37
Dudhi A	2	4	10	23	28	37
Dudhi B	2	16	11	6	27	48
Dudhi C	3	7	7	9	27	24
Dhani	3	20	7	9	22	42
Gordkhpuri	1	20	7	9	27	45
Gajgaur	3	18	12	19	28	49
Hansraj	3	18	6	8	2	37
Joginia	2	20	7	9	35	36
Kanyadali	3	4	10	6	35	47
Ketki	3	18	4	13	32	45
Kwari	2	20	7	9	36	42
Karahani A	1	7	9	14	6	37
Karahani B	3	4	8	8	40	37
Kudia	2	4	14	14	17	15
Kanchi A	1	5	4	8	15	2
Kanchi B	3	4	15	3	40	42

Table continued.

Cultivar	Pigments					
	S	L	N	I	G	K
Lurkan	3	13	5	14	32	37
Lalmati A	2	4	4	8	35	42
Lalmati B	3	4	7	9	28	42
Mutmuri	1	7	17	22	27	41
Mutmuria	2	18	7	8	27	45
Maliwa	2	5	13	8	27	36
Mutri A	1	18	7	8	37	52
N 22	1	7	5	8	27	44
Narendra 1	2	18	18	5	27	41
Nutan	3	4	9	7	38	36
Padhini	3	4	9	14	27	44
Pawas	3	18	13	14	22	42
Raimunia B	3	18	8	5	28	45
Rengi A	1	4	4	8	31	44
Rengi B	3	18	7	9	27	45
Rengi C	3	5	8	8	27	45
Ranikajal A	3	13	9	9	30	44
Ranikajal B	2	13	7	9	27	53
Ranikajal C	3	4	13	22	35	54
Ranikajal D	2	18	6	12	35	37
Sathi	3	4	9	14	29	37
Satha A	1	5	7	9	27	42
Satha B	3	5	9	14	17	37
Satha E	1	25	7	14	22	15
Satha F	3	13	9	9	39	37
Sankhal	2	8	7	8	27	36
Sakun	2	5	7	14	27	50
Sarya B	3	18	9	9	28	42
Sarya C	3	4	8	9	28	49
Sarya D	3	4	8	8	28	45
Sarya E	3	7	9	14	27	49
Safedwa	1	12	9	5	27	57
Sapna	3	7	9	14	28	46
Sonkharcha	3	4	7	9	35	56
Sawanibagri	3	8	9	5	29	45
Thelai	1	5	9	14	32	42
Tinpakhia A	2	18	9	14	22	37
Tinpakhia C	2	18	9	14	22	58
Tinpakhia E	3	4	4	8	27	36
<i>West Bengal</i>						
Dular	2	18	4	22	33	43

Pigments 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 12, 13, 15, 17, and 18 appeared in three traits; pigments 2, 3, 4, 14, 16, 20, 21, 22, 28, 35, 36 and 37 in two traits; and other pigments in only one trait.

This broad range of variability in pigment shades could be utilized in documentation and genetic studies and as markers in breeding programs. *J*

Effect of storage longevity on the response of rice seed to hot water treatment

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Hot water treatment is an effective plant quarantine measure for a range of rice

seed pathogens. However, it may affect seed viability and seedling vigor. Storage longevity also is known to reduce seed germination.

We studied the interaction between thermal treatment and storage longevity to determine whether hot water treatment of old seed is a safe practice. A completely randomized design was used, with seven replications per treatment. Seeds of IR36 and IR42 were obtained from the International Rice Testing Program storage at 20° C and 50% relative humidity (RH). Seed lot age varied from newly harvested to 5 yr old.

Fifty seeds of each entry were treated with hot water at 55°C for 20 min. Entries were subjected to a standard germination test immediately after thermal treatment and after a 30-d storage at 26 to 32° C and 78% relative humidity.

Initial viability of both cultivars was highest in the 1-yr-old seed lots and lowest in the 3-yr-old (Table 1). Initial viability was influenced by different seed sources as well as sample age.

The two cultivars responded similarly to the hot water treatment. Viability of

Table 1. Effect of seed age on germination after hot water treatment of 55°C for 20 min. IRRI

Seed age (yr)	Percentage germination ^a					
	IR36			IR42		
	Untreated	Hot water treated	Difference	Untreated	Hot water treated	Difference
0	85.7	88.9	3.2ns	87.4	90.0	2.6ns
1	96.5	96.9	0.3ns	92.6	95.4	2.8ns
3	73.1	49.7	-23.4**	73.7	66.3	-7.4*
5	86.0	84.3	-1.7ns	87.7	82.3	-5.4*

^aSignificant at 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels. ns = not significant.

newly harvested and 1-yr-old seed tested immediately after thermal treatment was not affected by the hot water (Table 1). Germination of 3-yr-old seed was reduced by the treatment. The 5-yr-old seed of IR42 was affected.

Germination was similar across the two storage periods. Viability of the 3- and 5-yr-old seed was further reduced by hot water treatment followed by 30 d posttreatment storage (Table 2). Reduction in viability was greatest in seed lots which had the lowest initial viability (3 yr old).

Hot water treatment should be used with caution when seeds have been stored longer than 1 yr or when the seed

Table 2. Effect of seed age on germination of 2 rice varieties hot water treated and stored for 30 d at room temperature. IRRI, 1986.

Seed age (yr)	Percentage germination ^a		
	Untreated	Hot water treated	Difference
0	86.9	88.1	1.2ns
1	93.9	96.3	2.4ns
3	53.1	40.9	-12.2**
5	79.1	70.4	-8.7**
Average	78.2		

^aSignificant at 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels. ns = not significant.

lots are of poor initial viability (i.e., below 85% germination). *S*

Genetic variability in 48 lowland rice cultivars of Uttar Pradesh, India

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Potent variability in local cultivars are the result of prolonged natural and artificial selection, although it is genetic variation which is heritable, and important. Genetic variability was assessed among 48 lowland rice cultivars sown July 1983. Plots were 5 × 2 m in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Grains/panicle, plant height, length of leaf, days to flowering, and leaf angle showed wide phenotypic variation (see table). Many cultivars shifted toward the higher limit for yield/plant and toward the lower limit for internode, tillers/plant, and leaf angle. Other traits were intermediate.

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, heritability, and genetic advance of 15 traits in 48 lowland rice cultivars. Faizabad, India.

Trait	Range	Grand mean and SEM	PCV	GCV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance in % of mean
Days to flowering	104.3-133.0	120.2± 1.3	5.7	5.5	94.8	11.1
Plant height	114.2-206.0	170.2± 7.3	11.7	10.4	79.8	19.2
Culm angle	52.0- 63.2	56.4± 2.9	6.9	2.9	17.3	2.5
Internode number	4.3- 7.0	5.0± 0.4	11.9	5.6	22.4	5.6
Tillers/plant	7.3- 25.6	12.6± 3.1	35.6	18.6	27.4	20.1
Length of leaf	48.7- 87.4	65.2± 5.2	14.2	10.4	53.0	15.6
Length of sheath	24.3- 48.6	30.7± 3.6	16.6	8.1	23.5	8.0
Leaf angle	7.7- 35.7	14.0± 3.5	45.1	33.2	54.2	50.3
Panicle length	20.4- 35.3	28.5± 1.3	10.2	8.5	70.1	14.6
Kernel length	4.5- 8.0	6.1± 0.1	12.3	12.2	97.4	24.8
Kernel breadth	1.5- 2.4	1.9± 0.1	12.3	9.7	62.2	16.0
Length-breadth ratio	2.5- 4.2	3.3± 0.1	12.6	12.2	94.4	24.3
Grains/panicle	127.5-335.6	208.4± 20.1	24.7	21.6	77.0	39.1
Test weight	11.8- 35.7	22.3± 2.8	30.5	26.2	73.2	46.4
Grain yield/plant	17.6- 43.7	33.4± 5.7	24.8	13.3	28.6	14.6

Phenotypic coefficients of variability (PCV) ranged from 5.7 (days to flowering) to 45.09 (leaf angle). The genotypic coefficient of variability (GCV) contributed most to PCV, with less environmental effect on internode, length (L) and breadth (B) of kernel, L:B, test weight, panicle length, and

culm angle. High heritability was coupled with high genetic advance for kernel length, L:B, plant height, grains/panicle, test weight, and panicle length. These traits could be effective for high selection response in lowland rice. *S*